

DISASTER RISK REDUCTION AND MANAGEMENT CAPABILITY OF THE CITY GOVERNMENT OF MUNTINLUPA: BASIS FOR AN ENHANCED DISASTER MANAGEMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

Disaster management, viewed from the community's perspective, is urgent and essential to have basic knowledge available to the community about what to do in the face of disasters. This study aimed to assess the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management capability. The potential impact of this research is to enhance the city's disaster management program. This study used a quantitative descriptive approach to gather and analyze the data and assess the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management capacity. A standardized questionnaire was used to collect the demographic profile, level of awareness, and the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management practices. The study reveals that higher awareness levels contribute to a more favorable assessment of DRRM efforts, reinforcing the importance of continuous information dissemination, training, and community engagement in disaster preparedness and response. The relatively low correlation suggests that other factors—such as direct experience with disaster response, resource availability, or policy enforcement—may also influence how DRRM practices are perceived. However, the finding underscores the critical need for more vigorous community participation, improved public communication, and greater transparency in DRRM programs to bridge the gap between government-led initiatives and residents' awareness and perception of these efforts. Strengthening disaster education, increasing community involvement in planning and drills, and enhancing accessibility to DRRM services may help align the perspectives

of both groups—the residents and providers—fostering a more resilient and prepared community (Asih et al., 2023).

Keywords: *Disaster Risk Reduction, Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (DRRMC), Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Capability, Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Practices, Disaster Management Program (DRM)*

INTRODUCTION

For millennia, the world has been plagued by both natural and man-made disasters. Catastrophes have severely impacted barangays and communities. With this, governments worldwide have implemented severe measures, such as formulating strategies, policies, and designs to mitigate the effects of natural and unnatural disasters. When the underlying weaknesses are addressed, resilience can be improved. Disaster risk reduction systematically incorporates disaster risk analysis and mitigation methods into barangays and community development planning (Valdez, 2018).

Communities and societies are severely disrupted by disasters, resulting in extensive losses of people, property, money, and/or the environment that exceed the impacted society's ability to recover its resources and rebuild. A confluence of risks and vulnerabilities causes them. Typhoons, earthquakes, and volcanic eruptions are natural disasters that can strike Southeast Asia, especially the Philippines (United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs, 2023). Because half of the 20 typhoons that hit the Philippines on average each year are destructive, disaster risk reduction must be a priority (Khan et al., 2024). The City Disaster Risk Reduction Management Office states that improving local government units' (LGUs') preparedness and response capabilities was the primary goal of its initiatives. Ten fundamental disaster training sessions are included in the training schedule plans of the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (CDRRM) program in Muntinlupa. These include vehicle extrication refresher courses, basic incident command system training, basic life support training, emergency operation center training, house-to-house search and rescue training, facilitator basic life support training, facilitator nutrition in emergencies, rapid damage analysis needs assessment training, collapsed structure search and rescue training, and basic incident command system training. Because the CDRRM's training is so generic, it might not cover the specific instructions required by the barangays and communities (Alshehri, 2026).

Prevention and Mitigation

Disasters frequently follow natural disasters. However, the degree to which a danger affects the environment and society determines the severity of a disaster. The magnitude of the impact will depend on the choices we make for our lives and the environment around us. These choices impact how we grow our food, where and how we build our homes, the kind of government we have, and how our financial system functions.

Every choice and action impacts our ability to withstand the calamities we face (Sabanal, 2023).

Disaster Preparedness

The US disaster response structure must be understood and known to respond to disasters as effectively as possible. The local government is the first to respond to a calamity. It establishes an Emergency Operations Center (EOC), activates mutual aid agreements, initiates the Incident Command System, and activates the local emergency management plan. The national government may be asked for assistance. Hospitals use the hospital incident command system in response (Sabanal, 2023).

Disaster Response

Disaster response, as defined by the Philippine Disaster Reduction Management Act (RA 10121), refers to the appropriate actions and planning undertaken before, during, and immediately after an event to respond to it in a manner that minimizes its effects and provides immediate relief and support to those affected. Response activities aim to save property and lives and restore safety to an impacted area. The operationalization and execution of plans and procedures, as well as the planning of activities to address an incident and its aftermath, constitute the response in this sense. Two essential elements of catastrophe operations are disaster response and disaster recovery. According to section 15 of the Act, disaster operations are any actions taken before, during, or following an event to minimize human casualties, illness, injury, property loss or damage, or environmental harm. This includes actions taken to lessen the adverse effects of the event. An integrated, proactive, and prosperous response to communities affected by disasters is ensured by the early and proactive activation of support and resources from both district and national levels, even though local governments are ultimately responsible for managing events within their respective areas (Sabanal, 2023).

Rehabilitation and Recovery

Different communities recover from disasters at varying speeds, and the process can be complicated and time-consuming. The recovery component is the most intricate and time-consuming component of the Prevention, Preparedness, Response, and Recovery (PPRR) comprehensive approach to disaster management. Ensuring rehabilitation plans are led by the impacted community and aligned with community needs yields the best results. All facets of society, including individuals, families, community organizations, businesses, and all tiers of government, must share responsibility for disaster recovery through a cooperative, coordinated, flexible, and scalable approach (Sabanal, 2023).

Research Questions

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Marital Status
 - 1.4 Education
 - 1.5 Barangay
 - 1.6 Years of Residence
2. What is the respondents' level of awareness on the disaster risk reduction and management of the City Government of Muntinlupa in terms of:
 - 2.1 Prevention and Mitigation
 - 2.2 Preparedness
 - 2.3 Response
 - 2.4 Rehabilitation and Recovery
3. What is the respondents' assessment of the disaster risk reduction and management practices of the City Government of Muntinlupa in terms of:
 - 3.1 Prevention and Mitigation
 - 3.2 Preparedness
 - 3.3 Response
 - 3.4 Rehabilitation and Recovery
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' level of awareness and assessment of the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Practices?
5. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of the two groups of respondents (community and DRRMC members) on Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Capability of the City Government of Muntinlupa?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what program may be proposed to enhance the city's disaster management?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a quantitative descriptive approach to assess the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Capacity and propose an enhanced disaster management program.

The researchers meticulously utilized a standardized quantitative instrument to collect data. A modified questionnaire was used to gather the respondents' demographic profiles and assess the city's disaster risk reduction and management capacity, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation for developing an enhanced management program. All items in the questionnaire were translated into Filipino to ensure that respondents could easily understand the questions to serve the study's purpose.

The Respondents

To fulfill the study's objective, the researchers selected one hundred (100) residents from the different barangays of the City Government of Muntinlupa and fifty (50) DRRMC members, with a total of one hundred fifty (150) respondents.

Profile of Respondents According to Address/Barangay

Address/Barangay	Barangay Residents	DRRMC Members
Brgy. Tunasan	13	8
Brgy. Poblacion	13	8
Brgy. Putatan	13	6
Brgy. Bayanan	13	6
Brgy. Alabang	13	6
Brgy. Ayala Alabang	9	4
Brgy. Cupang	9	4
Brgy. Buli	9	4
Brgy. Sucat	8	4
Total	100	50

Sampling Technique

Simple Random sampling is a technique in which every item in the population has an even chance of being selected in the sample. Here, the selection of items ultimately depends on chance or probability; therefore, this sampling technique is also sometimes known as a method of chance.

Before conducting the study, the researchers discussed the rationale and sought permission from the barangay captains to conduct the survey. The researchers randomly selected one hundred (100) residents and fifty (50) DRRMC members. Muntinlupa City has nine (9) barangays, as reflected in the respondents' profiles in terms of address.

Data Gathering Instrument

The researchers used a survey questionnaire to collect the necessary information for the study. This method was designed to analyze the gathered data statistically.

In this study, the researchers designed a modified questionnaire with options that could be easily answered by placing a checkmark in each box. The questionnaire was divided into two parts. The first part concerned the respondents' demographic profile. The second part assessed the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Capacity.

Validation of Research Instrument

The instrument used in this study is a survey questionnaire, which has undergone several validation tests by the college statistician and research expert of Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Muntinlupa (PLMun) to check whether the formulated questions align with the SOP.

Data Gathering Procedure

One hundred (150) survey materials were distributed to the qualified respondents to obtain the necessary information for analysis. The researchers discussed the instructions on the questionnaire to ensure that the respondents fully understood the mechanics.

The results were tallied and tabulated based on the respondents' answers to the questionnaire's questions. Once completed, tallies and tables were interpreted and analyzed using statistical tools.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To interpret the data effectively, the researchers utilized the following statistical tools: Percentage, Weighted Mean, Independent Samples Test, One-way ANOVA, and Pearson Correlation Coefficient, often referred to as Pearson's r .

Percentage. In mathematics, a percentage is a number or ratio that represents a fraction of 100. It is often denoted by the symbol "%" or simply as "percent" or "pct." [3] This tool was used to assess the demographic profile of the respondents statistically (Kremelberg, 2009).

$$P = F/N \times 100$$

Where:

F - frequency

N - total population of the respondents

100 - a constant number

Weighted Mean. A mean where some values contribute more than others. This statistical tool was used to analyze and interpret the data collected on the assessment of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Capacity of the City Government of Muntinlupa (Kremelberg, 2009).

$$X = Fx/N$$

Where:

X - weighted mean

F - frequency

X - weight of each item

N - total number of respondents

The Independent Samples Test (T-test). This compares the means and errors of two groups to determine whether they are significantly different (Kremelberg, 2009).

$$t = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{S_1^2}{N_1} + \frac{S_2^2}{N_2}}}$$

Where,

\bar{x} = Mean of first set of values

\bar{x}_2 = Mean of second set of values

S_1 = Standard deviation of first set of values

S_2 = Standard deviation of second set of values

n_1 = Total number of values in first set

n_2 = Total number of values in second set.

One-way ANOVA. This is a generalization of the two-sample t-test. The F-statistic compares the variability between groups to the variability within each group (Kremelberg, 2009).

$$F = \frac{MST}{MSE}$$

$$MST = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k (T_i^2/n_i) - G^2/n}{k - 1}$$

$$MSE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} Y_{ij}^2 - \sum_{i=1}^k (T_i^2/n_i)}{n - k}$$

Where F is the variance ratio for the overall test, MST is the mean square due to treatments/groups (between groups), MSE is the mean square due to error (within groups, residual mean square), Y_{ij} is an observation, T_i is a group total, G is the grand total of all observations, n_i is the number in group i and n is the total number of observations.

Pearson Correlation Coefficient / Pearson R. This statistical formula measures the strength of the relationship between variables. It was used to find the relationship between the level of awareness and assessment of the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Practices (Kremelberg, 2009).

$$r_{xy} = \frac{N \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{\{N \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2\} \{N \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2\}}}$$

Where:

r_{xy} = product-moment coefficient of correlation between X and Y variables

$\sum XY$ = Sum of the product of X and Y

$\sum X$ = Sum of the scores of X variables

$\sum Y$ = Sum of the scores of Y variables

$\sum X^2$ = Sum of the squares of X

$\sum Y^2$ = Sum of the squares of Y

Likert Scale. This is a frequency scale that uses fixed-choice response formats. The researchers used the four-point scale to assess the respondents' awareness of the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management practices.

Where:

- 4 – Strongly Agree
- 3 – Agree
- 2 – Disagree
- 1 – Strongly Disagree

RESULTS

Table 1.1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

AGE	Barangay Resident		DRRMC Members		Total	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
18-24 years old	15	15%	5	10%	20	13.33%
25-34 years old	35	35%	22	44%	57	38.00%
35-44 years old	22	22%	18	36%	40	26.67%
45-54 years old	18	18%	5	10%	23	15.33%
55-64 years old	6	6%	0	0%	6	4.00%
65-74 years old	3	3%	0	0%	3	2.00%
75 years or older	1	1%	0	0%	1	0.67%
TOTAL	100	100%	50	100%	150	100%

Table 1.2: Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Sex	Barangay Resident		DRRMC Members		Total	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Male	35	35%	46	92%	81	54.00%
Female	65	65%	4	8%	69	46.00%
TOTAL	100	100%	50	100%	150	100%

Table 1.3: Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Marital Status

Marital Status	Barangay Resident		DRRMC Members		Total	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Single	25	25%	4	8%	29	19.33%
Married or domestic partnership	63	63%	39	78%	102	68.00%
Widowed	9	9%	2	4%	11	7.33%
Separated	3	3%	5	10%	8	5.33%
TOTAL	100	100%	50	100%	150	100%

Table 1.4: Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Education

Education	Barangay Resident		DRRMC Members		Total	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
No schooling completed	8	8%	0	0%	8	5.33%
Grade School Graduate	10	10%	0	0%	10	6.67%
Trade/Technical/Vocational Training	5	5%	6	12%	11	7.33%
Associate Degree	15	15%	6	12%	21	14.00%
Bachelor's Degree	54	54%	38	76%	92	61.33%
Master's Degree	4	4%	0	0%	4	2.67%
Doctorate Degree	4	4%	0	0%	4	2.67%
TOTAL	100	100%	50	100%	150	100%

Table 1.5: Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Barangay

Barangay	Barangay Resident		DRRMC Members		Total	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Brgy. Tunasan	13	13%	8	16%	21	14.00%
Brgy. Poblacion	13	13%	8	16%	21	14.00%
Brgy. Putatan	13	13%	6	12%	19	12.67%
Brgy. Bayanan	13	13%	6	12%	19	12.67%

Brgy. Alabang	13	13%	6	12%	19	12.67%
Brgy. Ayala Alabang	9	9%	4	8%	13	8.67%
Brgy. Cupang	9	9%	4	8%	13	8.67%
Brgy. Buli	9	9%	4	8%	13	8.67%
Brgy. Sucat	8	8%	4	8%	12	8.00%
TOTAL	100	100%	50	100%	150	100%

Table 1.6: Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Years of Residence

Years of Residence	Barangay Resident		DRRMC Members		Total	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1 - 10 years	12	12%	0	0%	12	8.00%
11 - 20 years	20	20%	0	0%	20	13.33%
21 - 30 years	32	32%	0	0%	32	21.33%
31 - 40 years	15	15%	6	12%	21	14.00%
41 - 50 years	8	8%	38	76%	46	30.67%
51 - 60 years	8	8%	4	8%	12	8.00%
61 years and above	5	5%	2	4%	7	4.67%
TOTAL	100	100%	50	100%	150	100%

Table 2.1: Respondents' Level of Awareness on the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management of the City Government of Muntinlupa in terms of Prevention and Mitigation

Prevention and Mitigation	Barangay Residents		DRRMC Members		Overall		Rank
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	

1. Prevention and Mitigation are key strategic actions that prioritize activities such as hazard evaluation and mitigation, identification, and analysis of vulnerable areas, and mainstreaming Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) into development plans.	2.79	Agree	3.48	Agree	3.13 5	Agree	4
2. DRRM is integrated into national, sectoral, regional, and local development policies, plans, programs, and budgets to reduce the capacity to mitigate risk and hazard exposure.	2.8	Agree	3.46	Agree	3.13	Agree	7
3. DRRM, as part of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), promotes all-encompassing environmental action and cooperation to mitigate the number and impact of natural and artificial disasters.	2.79	Agree	3.49	Agree	3.14 5	Agree	3
4. Integrating DRRM into different environment-related policies and plans, including land and air use and natural resource management, reduces hazard vulnerability.	2.74	Agree	3.56	Strongly Agree	3.15	Agree	2
5. The DRRM team identifies urban communities surrounded by precarious buildings by conducting vulnerability and risk assessments to reduce the disaster resiliency of infrastructure systems.	2.77	Agree	3.56	Strongly Agree	3.16 5	Agree	1
6. A community-based and scientific DRRM hazard and risk assessment, analysis, mapping, and monitoring establishes a	2.71	Agree	3.52	Strongly Agree	3.11 5	Agree	8

practical guide for national and local planning.							
7. Information dissemination through partnerships with various media enhances community-based awareness of DRRM prevention and mitigation.	2.71	Agree	3.56	Strongly Agree	3.13 5	Agree	4
8. The disaster control unit only uses safety checklists and self-monitoring tools to assess and identify risk vulnerability.	2.73	Agree	3.54	Strongly Agree	3.13 5	Agree	4
9. Disaster risk financing of Local Government Units (LGUs) can contribute to preventing and mitigating disasters, especially at the community level.	2.73	Agree	3.44	Agree	3.08 5	Agree	10
10. To be effective, early warning systems (EWS) must actively involve at-risk communities, facilitate and disseminate public education, awareness, and risk warnings, and ensure constant preparedness.	2.74	Agree	3.46	Agree	3.1	Agree	9
TOTAL	2.75	Agree	3.51	Strongly Agree	3.13	Agree	

Table 2.2: Respondents' Level of Awareness on the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management of the City Government of Muntinlupa in terms of Preparedness

Preparedness	Barangay Residents		DRRMC Members		Overall		Rank
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	

1. Disaster Risk Reduction and Management information, education, communication (IEC), and advocacy enhance the community's awareness and capacity for dealing with the threats and impacts of all hazards.	2.72	Agree	3.64	Strongly Agree	3.18	Agree	8
2. Comprehensive DRRM policies, plans, and systems, implemented through scenario-based drills and response activities, will equip the community with the necessary skills to mitigate the negative impacts of a disaster.	2.74	Agree	3.62	Strongly Agree	3.18	Agree	8
3. Specialized training and simulation exercises are provided to specific groups (e.g., decision-makers, responders, public and private sector employees) to help them prepare for disasters.	2.72	Agree	3.7	Strongly Agree	3.21	Agree	3
4. A Public Storm Signal warning tells the general public what to expect and provides an advisory of necessary precautions during typhoons.	2.81	Agree	3.72	Strongly Agree	3.265	Agree	1
5. A flood or flash flood warning is used when flooding or flash flooding is already occurring in your area.	2.78	Agree	3.62	Strongly Agree	3.2	Agree	6

6. Drop, Hold On, and Cover is a simulated earthquake response drill.	2.73	Agree	3.6	Strongly Agree	3.165	Agree	10
7. In an earthquake-simulated scenario, standing in a doorway and running outside are considered safe and recommended.	2.8	Agree	3.62	Strongly Agree	3.21	Agree	3
8. Rescue, Alert, Contain, Extinguish is a simulated-based response to a Fire Hazard drill.	2.78	Agree	3.66	Strongly Agree	3.22	Agree	2
9. When utilizing a fire extinguisher, the acronym P.A.S.S. stands for Pull, Aim, Sweep, and Squeeze.	2.82	Agree	3.6	Strongly Agree	3.21	Agree	3
10. An evacuation center must have the necessary physical amenities and space for health promotion and disease prevention, which are essential for the well-being of evacuees.	2.77	Agree	3.62	Strongly Agree	3.195	Agree	7
TOTAL	2.77	Agree	3.64	Strongly Agree	3.20	Agree	

Table 2.3: Respondents' Level of Awareness on the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management of the City Government of Muntinlupa in terms of Response

Response	Barangay Residents		DRRMC Members		Overall		Rank
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
1. The key to effective disaster response operations is recognizing the importance of a seamless flow of information and establishing a coordination system.	2.74	Agree	3.62	Strongly Agree	3.18	Agree	8
2. Food, shelter, water, sanitation, and health preservation are the basic requirements addressed when an emergency disaster strikes.	2.75	Agree	3.72	Strongly Agree	3.235	Agree	1
3. The DRRM team sorts sick and injured people based on their frequency and type of condition, a process called "Triage."	2.73	Agree	3.6	Strongly Agree	3.165	Agree	10
4. Disaster victims categorized in "black code" are considered the first, immediate, and high priority under Triage.	2.77	Agree	3.58	Strongly Agree	3.175	Agree	9
5. The DRRM team must ensure that no one gets stranded and that all those who want/need evacuation are attended to in an orderly, safe, and effective manner.	2.75	Agree	3.62	Strongly Agree	3.185	Agree	7

6. Standard-based evacuation sites must be identified and considered only during and after a disaster.	2.74	Agree	3.64	Strongly Agree	3.19	Agree	5
7. Basic social services, such as medical consultations and nutritional assessments, are provided to the affected population to maintain the health status of the affected communities.	2.72	Agree	3.68	Strongly Agree	3.2	Agree	3
8. Traumatic and/or psychological stress debriefing is provided to address the physiological needs of the affected population, especially the elderly, persons with disabilities, women, and children.	2.73	Agree	3.7	Strongly Agree	3.215	Agree	2
9. The Search, Rescue, and Retrieval (SRR) system is implemented to provide services for the missing, ensuring that they are found.	2.76	Agree	3.62	Strongly Agree	3.19	Agree	6
10. The success of a functional, integrated, and coordinated system to assist victims throughout their early recovery depends on the political commitment of both local and national governments.	2.79	Agree	3.6	Strongly Agree	3.195	Agree	4

TOTAL	2.75	Agree	3.64	Strongly Agree	3.19	Agree	
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Table 2.4: Respondents’ Level of Awareness on the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management of the City Government of Muntinlupa in terms of Rehabilitation and Recovery

Rehabilitation and Recovery	Barangay Residents		DRRMC Members		Overall		Rank
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
1. Rehabilitation and recovery focus on rebuilding the affected communities, restoring livelihoods, effectively preventing the recurrence of disasters, and harnessing conditions for future development.	2.82	Agree	3.64	Strongly Agree	3.23	Agree	7
2. Managing recovery requires building local capacities, restoring coping mechanisms, empowering communities, and identifying the root causes and vulnerabilities that make communities disaster-resilient.	2.82	Agree	3.72	Strongly Agree	3.27	Agree	1
3. A Post-Disaster Needs Assessment (PDNA) is conducted before a disaster occurs to assess, analyze, and prioritize damages, losses, and the needs of victims.	2.78	Agree	3.7	Strongly Agree	3.24	Agree	5

4. DRRM authorities coordinate the formulation of the Strategic Action Plan for disaster-affected areas locally and nationally.	2.78	Agree	3.62	Strongly Agree	3.2	Agree	9
5. DRRM is mainstreamed in human settlements and safety for people displaced by natural and human-induced disasters, as well as those living in areas prone to disasters.	2.81	Agree	3.7	Strongly Agree	3.255	Agree	3
6. Rehabilitation or repair of damaged infrastructure, implementation of building codes, and promotion of green technology are essential short-term goals.	2.74	Agree	3.72	Strongly Agree	3.23	Agree	6
7. LGUs, NGOs, concerned agencies, and other private sector organizations fund disaster victims' recovery.	2.76	Agree	3.64	Strongly Agree	3.2	Agree	9
8. People's ability to recover quickly from disasters depends heavily on restoring their sources of income and livelihood opportunities.	2.8	Agree	3.72	Strongly Agree	3.26	Agree	2
9. Along with relief, rehabilitation, and care of physical health and injuries, psychosocial and mental health issues are also important, and they need to be addressed.	2.75	Agree	3.66	Strongly Agree	3.205	Agree	8

10. A psychologically sound, safe, and secure citizenry protected from the effects of disasters can restore normal functioning after each catastrophe.	2.8	Agree	3.7	Strongly Agree	3.25	Agree	4
TOTAL	2.79	Agree	3.68	Strongly Agree	3.23	Agree	

Table 3.1: Respondents' Assessment of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Practices of the City Government of Muntinlupa in terms of Mitigation and Prevention

Mitigation and Prevention	Barangay Residents		DRRMC Members		Overall		Rank
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
1. Mainstreaming and integrating Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) into local development policies, plans, programs, and budgets, including barangays and communities.	2.67	Agree	2.72	Agree	2.695	Agree	2
2. Utilization of the local DRRM funds for barangays and communities.	2.71	Agree	2.8	Agree	2.755	Agree	1
3. Conduct inventory, vulnerability, and risk assessments of critical facilities in the barangays and communities.	2.69	Agree	2.64	Agree	2.665	Agree	9

4. Develop guidelines on infrastructure redesign, retrofitting, or operational modifications for barangays and communities.	2.67	Agree	2.68	Agree	2.675	Agree	6
5. Integrating building codes and green technology in barangays and communities.	2.64	Agree	2.74	Agree	2.69	Agree	3
6. Conduct studies with the barangays and communities on disaster risk prevention interventions for armed conflict situations and climate change.	2.69	Agree	2.66	Agree	2.675	Agree	6
7. Information Dissemination: DRRM is implemented through partnerships with various media to inform the barangay and communities in the event of an emergency.	2.66	Agree	2.7	Agree	2.68	Agree	4
8. Conduct research and develop innovative modalities for risk financing schemes tailored to barangays and communities.	2.72	Agree	2.64	Agree	2.68	Agree	4
9. Develop advocacy and risk communication plans for barangays and communities.	2.51	Agree	2.68	Agree	2.595	Agree	10

10. Develop community-based and local early warning systems for various hazards in barangays and communities.	2.62	Agree	2.72	Agree	2.695	Agree	8
TOTAL	2.66	Agree	2.70	Agree	2.68	Agree	

Table 3.2: Respondents' Assessment of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Practices of the City Government of Muntinlupa in terms of Preparedness

Preparedness	Barangay Residents		DRRMC Members		Overall		Rank
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
1. Develop DRRM information, education, communication (IEC), and advocacy plans for barangays and communities.	2.68	Agree	2.72	Agree	2.7	Agree	6
2. Develop standard DRRM training modules for barangays and communities.	2.67	Agree	2.74	Agree	2.705	Agree	5
3. Conduct training and simulation exercises in barangays and communities.	2.65	Agree	2.72	Agree	2.685	Agree	8
4. Selection and accreditation of NGO representatives to realize the DRRM plans and programs for barangays and communities.	2.66	Agree	2.74	Agree	2.7	Agree	6
5. Development of the local DRRM and contingency plan for barangays and communities.	2.64	Agree	2.72	Agree	2.68	Agree	10

6. Managing resources of the Local DRRM Councils and Offices for barangays and communities.	2.65	Agree	2.78	Agree	2.715	Agree	3
7. Develop and/or enhance guidelines for emergency response and simulated scenario-based preparedness for barangays and communities.	2.63	Agree	2.74	Agree	2.685	Agree	8
8. Develop and/or enhance ICS coordination and communication systems for barangays and communities.	2.69	Agree	2.78	Agree	2.735	Agree	1
9. Develop and/or enhance a manual of operations for Disaster Operations Centers for barangays and communities.	2.7	Agree	2.74	Agree	2.72	Agree	2
10. Develop and/or enhance protocols for gathering and reporting information.	2.66	Agree	2.76	Agree	2.71	Agree	4
TOTAL	2.66	Agree	2.74	Agree	2.70	Agree	

Table 3.3: Respondents' Assessment of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Practices of the City Government of Muntinlupa in terms of Response

Response	Barangay Residents		DRRMC Members		Overall		Rank
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
1. Activation of the Incident Command Systems (ICS), advisories, and the cluster approach extended to the barangay and community levels.	2.64	Agree	2.76	Agree	2.7	Agree	6
2. Establishment of coordination systems for effective and efficient relief and response operations.	2.66	Agree	2.78	Agree	2.72	Agree	3
3. Activation of assessment teams at the barangay and community levels.	2.7	Agree	2.72	Agree	2.71	Agree	5
4. Conduct an assessment using the latest damage assessment and needs analysis (DANA) tool with the barangay and community, using the information to inform the appropriate response of the DRRM council.	2.23	Disagree	2.3	Agree	2.265	Agree	10
5. Develop and implement systems for search, rescue, and retrieval (SRR).	2.72	Agree	2.74	Agree	2.73	Agree	1
6. Identify standard-based relief shelters and sites in the barangays and communities.	2.69	Agree	2.76	Agree	2.725	Agree	2

7. Conduct medical consultations, nutritional assessments, and traumatic and/or psychological stress debriefings in the barangays and communities.	2.26	Disagree	2.38	Agree	2.32	Agree	8
8. Conduct post-DANA for the affected barangays and communities.	2.24	Disagree	2.3	Agree	2.27	Agree	9
9. Develop partnership mechanisms with utility providers and key stakeholders.	2.67	Agree	2.7	Agree	2.685	Agree	7
10. Design and implement temporary livelihood and/or income-generating activities (i.e., cash/food for work; micro and small enterprise recovery) for barangays and communities.	2.69	Agree	2.74	Agree	2.715	Agree	4
TOTAL	2.55	Agree	2.62	Agree	2.58	Agree	

Table 3.4: Respondents' Assessment of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Practices of the City Government of Muntinlupa in terms of Rehabilitation and Recovery

Rehabilitation and Recovery	Barangay Residents		DRRMC Members		Overall		Rank
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
1. Conduct a Post-Disaster Needs Assessment (PDNA) one month after a disaster occurs with the affected barangays and communities. The OCD will take the lead and use	2.28	Disagree	2.46	Disagree	2.37	Disagree	8

preliminary data gathered from the field by OCD regional offices.							
2. Coordinate the formulation of the Strategic Action Plan for disaster-affected barangays and communities.	2.68	Agree	2.78	Agree	2.73	Agree	3
3. Identify and mobilize funding sources for barangays and communities.	2.67	Agree	2.8	Agree	2.735	Agree	1
4. Identify and provide suitable relocation sites for the affected barangays and communities.	2.65	Agree	2.82	Agree	2.735	Agree	1
5. Conduct training for social preparation of host communities and those relocated to reduce conflict.	2.65	Agree	2.74	Agree	2.695	Agree	6
6. Undertake the necessary rehabilitation or repair of damaged infrastructure in the barangays and communities.	2.66	Agree	2.74	Agree	2.7	Agree	5
7. Develop systems for appropriate risk protection measures for barangays and communities.	2.65	Agree	2.72	Agree	2.685	Agree	7
8. Conduct post-disaster or conflict needs analyses with affected barangays and communities.	2.29	Disagree	2.44	Disagree	2.365	Disagree	9
9. Develop systems of support and communication among key stakeholders.	2.66	Agree	2.76	Agree	2.71	Agree	4

10. Build capacities of psychosocial care providers for affected barangays and communities.	2.27	Agree	2.4	Disagree	2.335	Disagree	10
TOTAL	2.55	Agree	2.67	Agree	2.61	Agree	

Table 4: Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Level of Awareness and Assessment of the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Practices

Category	Mean	Standard deviation	Pearson r value	Critical Value	Decision
Level of Awareness of the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Practices	3.19	0.434	0.247	±1.96	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Assessment of the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Practices	2.64	0.148			

Table 5: Significant Difference Between the Assessment of the two Groups of Respondents (residents and DRRMC members) on Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Capability of the City Government of Muntinlupa

Category	n	Mean	SD	T-test value	Critical Value	Decision
Residents	100	2.68	0.134	0.0003	±1.04	Accept the Null Hypothesis

DISCUSSION

Table 1.1 presents the age distribution of the respondents, categorized into barangay residents and members of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (DRRMC). Among the 150 respondents, the most significant proportion falls within the 25-34 age group, accounting for 38% (57 individuals) of the total sample. This age group is also the most represented among DRRMC members and barangay residents, comprising 44% (22 individuals) and 35% (35 individuals), respectively. This indicates that younger professionals play a key role in disaster management efforts.

The second most represented age group is 35-44 years old, comprising 26.67% (40 individuals) of the total respondents, with 36% (18 individuals) from the DRRMC, suggesting that mid-career individuals also have significant involvement in disaster risk reduction initiatives. Meanwhile, 15.33% (23 individuals) belong to the 45-54 age range,

with only 10% (5 individuals) from the DRRMC, indicating a decreasing trend in participation among older individuals in disaster response roles.

Notably, barangay residents in the 18-24 age group constitute 15% (15 individuals) of the community respondents, but only 10% (5 individuals) of the DRRMC members. This may suggest that younger individuals in the community are aware of DRRM concerns but have limited active participation in formal disaster management. The representation further declines among older age groups, with only 4% (6 individuals) aged 55-64 years, 2% (3 individuals) aged 65-74 years, and just 0.67% (1 individual) aged 75 years or older. There are no DRRMC members from these older age brackets, which may indicate challenges in senior participation in disaster management activities due to physical limitations or other factors.

Overall, the data highlight that disaster risk reduction and management efforts in Muntinlupa are predominantly led by individuals aged 25-44, reflecting an active workforce engaged in disaster preparedness and response. Meanwhile, participation significantly declines among older age groups, indicating a potential need for more inclusive disaster management initiatives that encourage broader community involvement across different age groups.

Table 1.2 presents the gender distribution of the respondents, categorized into barangay residents and members of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (DRRMC). Among the 150 total respondents, 54% (81) are male, while 46% (69) are female, indicating a relatively balanced representation of genders within the study sample.

However, a notable disparity is observed when comparing the gender distribution between barangay residents and DRRMC members. Among barangay residents, females outnumber males, comprising 65% (65 individuals), while males make up only 35% (35 individuals). This suggests that within the general community, women are more actively represented in the study, which may imply greater engagement in disaster-related discussions or community surveys.

Conversely, within the DRRMC, 92% (46 individuals) of the members are male, while only 8% (4 individuals) are female. This indicates a significant gender gap in leadership and operational roles in disaster risk reduction and management, where men overwhelmingly dominate decision-making and disaster response efforts. The low female representation in the DRRMC suggests potential barriers to women's participation in disaster management, which could be due to traditional gender roles, physical demands of the job, or other socio-cultural factors.

Overall, while both men and women actively engage in disaster-related matters at the community level, the gender imbalance in DRRM leadership highlights the need for policies that promote greater inclusivity and gender equality in disaster risk reduction and management efforts in Muntinlupa. Encouraging more female participation in DRRM roles could help diversify perspectives and enhance disaster preparedness strategies.

Table 1.3 presents the marital status distribution of the respondents, categorized into barangay residents and Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (DRRMC) members. Among the 150 total respondents, the majority, 68% (102 individuals), are married or in a domestic partnership, followed by 19.33% (29 individuals) who are single. Meanwhile, 7.33% (11 individuals) are widowed, and 5.33% (8 individuals) are separated. A closer look at the barangay residents shows that most respondents, 63% (63 individuals), are married or in a domestic partnership, while 25% (25 individuals) are single. This suggests that a large portion of the community members involved in disaster-related discussions are family-oriented individuals who may have a vested interest in disaster preparedness to ensure the safety of their households.

Among the DRRMC members, the trend is similar, with 78% (39 individuals) being married or in a domestic partnership. However, only 8% (4 individuals) are single, which is notably lower than the percentage of single residents in the barangay. This suggests that disaster risk reduction and management roles are primarily filled by individuals who have family responsibilities, potentially reflecting a sense of duty toward community safety.

Notably, the percentage of widowed individuals among the barangay residents, 9% (9 individuals), is higher than in the DRRMC, 4% (2 individuals), indicating that older or widowed individuals may be less involved in direct disaster management roles. Interestingly, the separated category has a higher percentage among DRRMC members, at 10% (5 individuals), than among barangay residents, at 3% (3 individuals), suggesting that individuals in this category may be more inclined to engage in DRRM efforts, possibly due to fewer household obligations.

Overall, the data suggest that disaster management in Muntinlupa is primarily driven by married individuals, highlighting the importance of family-oriented disaster preparedness strategies. The relatively low participation of single and widowed individuals in DRRMC roles may indicate a need to encourage broader community engagement across different marital statuses to enhance disaster resilience.

Table 1.4 presents the respondents' educational attainment, categorized into barangay residents and Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (DRRMC) members. The majority of the respondents, 61.33% (92 individuals), hold a Bachelor's Degree, indicating that most participants have attained higher education.

Among barangay residents, 54% (54 individuals) have a Bachelor's Degree, while 15% (15 individuals) hold an Associate Degree. A small percentage of barangay residents have no formal schooling, comprising 8% (8 individuals), or have only completed Grade School, at 10% (10 individuals), which suggests that a portion of the community may have limited access to education. Additionally, 5% (5 individuals) have completed vocational training, and a few have pursued Master's degrees 4%, (4 individuals), or Doctorate Degrees 4%, (4 individuals), indicating the presence of higher-educated individuals within the barangay.

Among DRRMC members, 76% (38 individuals) hold a Bachelor's Degree, suggesting that educational qualifications are a key factor in recruitment for disaster management roles. Meanwhile, 12% (6 individuals) hold an Associate Degree, and another 12% (6 individuals) have received Trade, Technical, or Vocational Training, which may reflect the need for practical skills in disaster response and emergency management. Notably, none of the DRRMC members have Master's or Doctorate Degrees, indicating that advanced academic qualifications are not a common requirement for these roles.

Overall, the data highlight that disaster risk reduction and management in Muntinlupa are primarily handled by individuals with a college-level education, particularly those with a Bachelor's Degree. However, the presence of barangay residents with lower educational attainment suggests that efforts should be made to enhance disaster education and awareness programs at the grassroots level. Additionally, integrating more professionals with advanced degrees into DRRMC roles may further strengthen the city's disaster preparedness and strategic planning efforts.

Table 1.5 presents the distribution of respondents across the nine barangays of Muntinlupa, categorized into barangay residents and Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (DRRMC) members. The data show that the respondents are fairly distributed across all barangays, ensuring a balanced representation of perspectives from different areas within the city.

The highest number of respondents comes from Brgy. Tunasan and Brgy. Poblacion, each contributing 14% (21 individuals) to the total sample, followed closely by Brgy. Putatan, Bayanan, and Alabang, each accounting for 12.67% (19 individuals) of the respondents. These barangays have a strong community representation and a notable number of DRRMC members, suggesting active disaster management engagement in these areas.

Meanwhile, Brgy. Ayala Alabang, Brgy. Cupang, and Brgy. Buli each has 8.67% (13 individuals) of the total respondents, while Brgy. Sucat has the lowest representation, comprising 8% (12 individuals). The relatively lower number of respondents from these barangays may suggest differences in population size, community engagement, or accessibility in discussions related to disasters.

Among DRRMC members, the highest representation is also from Brgy. Tunasan and Brgy. Poblacion had 16% (8 individuals) each, followed by Brgy. Putatan, Bayanan, and Alabang had 12% (6 individuals) each. The lowest DRRMC representation comes from Brgy. Ayala Alabang, Cupang, Buli, and Sucat, each with 8% (4 individuals). This could indicate variations in disaster management infrastructure, participation levels, or the assignment of DRRMC personnel across barangays.

Overall, the data suggest that all barangays in Muntinlupa have some level of disaster management participation, with Brgy. Tunasan and Brgy. Poblacion leading in engagement. However, efforts may be needed to strengthen DRRM initiatives in

barangays with lower representation, such as Brgy. Sucat, to ensure equitable disaster preparedness and response across the entire city.

Table 1.6 presents the respondents' residence length in Muntinlupa, categorized into barangay residents and Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (DRRMC) members. The data highlight variations in community experience and local knowledge based on the length of time respondents have lived in the city.

Among the barangay residents, the most significant proportion, 32% (32 individuals), have lived in Muntinlupa for 21-30 years, followed by 20% (20 individuals) who have resided for 11-20 years. Meanwhile, 15% (15 individuals) have been in the city for 31-40 years, while smaller groups have lived there for either 41-50 years 8% (8 individuals), 51-60 years 8% (8 individuals), or 61 years and above 5% (5 individuals). The lowest percentage, 12% (12 individuals), represents those who have only been residents for 1-10 years. This suggests that most barangay residents surveyed are familiar with the community and its disaster risks, making their insights valuable in assessing local disaster preparedness.

In contrast, DRRMC members show a strikingly different trend. The majority, 76% (38 individuals), have resided in Muntinlupa for 41-50 years, indicating that most disaster management officers have deep-rooted experience in the area. This could be advantageous, as their familiarity with historical disaster events and local vulnerabilities may enhance risk reduction strategies. Additionally, 12% (6 individuals) have lived in Muntinlupa for 31-40 years, while 8% (4 individuals) have been residents for 51-60 years. Only 4% (2 individuals) have resided in the city for 61 years or more; notably, no DRRMC members have lived in the city for 1-30 years.

This contrast suggests that DRRMC positions are primarily held by long-term residents, possibly due to the need for extensive experience and historical knowledge in disaster risk reduction efforts. However, the absence of newer residents (those with 1-30 years of residence) in DRRMC roles may indicate a gap in leadership succession or limited opportunities for younger or newer community members to participate in disaster management efforts.

Overall, while long-term residents dominate barangay and DRRMC groups, efforts could be made to involve newer residents in disaster preparedness programs. Doing so may encourage fresh perspectives, knowledge transfer, and continuity in disaster risk reduction strategies for future generations.

Table 2.1 indicates that both barangay residents and DRRMC members generally agree on the importance of prevention and mitigation in Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) within the City Government of Muntinlupa. The overall mean score of 3.13 ("Agree") suggests that while awareness exists, there is still room for improvement in strengthening disaster prevention and mitigation efforts.

Among the DRRMC members, the level of awareness is notably higher, with a mean score of 3.51 ("Strongly Agree"), compared to barangay residents, who recorded a lower mean score of 2.75 ("Agree"). This discrepancy suggests that DRRMC members, more directly involved in disaster management, have a deeper understanding of DRRM strategies. In contrast, barangay residents may require further education and engagement to reach the same level of awareness.

The highest-ranking item, "The DRRM team identifies urban communities surrounded by precarious buildings by conducting vulnerability and risk assessments to reduce the disaster resiliency of infrastructure systems" (overall mean = 3.165, Rank 1), indicates that respondents recognize the importance of assessing high-risk areas to minimize disaster impacts. Additionally, "Integrating DRRM into different environment-related policies and plans, including land and air use and natural resource management, reduces hazard vulnerability" (overall mean = 3.15, Rank 2) received strong agreement, particularly from DRRMC members (3.56 – "Strongly Agree"), highlighting the critical role of policy integration in disaster prevention.

Other key indicators, such as "DRRM, as part of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), adopts all-environmental action and cooperation to increase the number and effects of natural and artificial disasters" (mean = 3.145, Rank 3) and "Information dissemination through partnerships with various media enhances community-based awareness of DRRM prevention and mitigation" (mean = 3.135, Rank 4), suggest that respondents acknowledge the significance of environmental cooperation and effective communication in enhancing disaster resilience. However, the relatively lower mean scores of barangay residents in these areas indicate the need for improved public awareness campaigns and accessibility to DRRM-related information.

The lowest-ranked item, "Disaster Risk Financing of Local Government Units (LGUs) can contribute to preventing and mitigating disasters, especially at the community level" (overall mean = 3.085, Rank 10), suggests that while respondents recognize its importance, financial mechanisms for disaster prevention may not be well understood or effectively communicated at the community level. Similarly, "To be effective, early warning systems (EWS) must actively involve at-risk communities, facilitate and disseminate public education, awareness, and risk warnings, and ensure constant preparedness" (mean = 3.1, Rank 9) indicates that early warning systems need further emphasis to ensure full community engagement.

Overall, the study highlights a higher level of awareness among DRRMC members compared to barangay residents, indicating the need for enhanced community education, information dissemination, and policy integration at the local level. Strengthening awareness programs, increasing community participation in disaster risk assessments, and ensuring financial investments in disaster prevention can further improve Muntinlupa's disaster resilience and preparedness.

Table 2.2 indicates that both barangay residents and DRRMC members generally agree on the importance of disaster preparedness in the City Government of Muntinlupa's

Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) initiatives. The overall mean score of 3.20 ("Agree") suggests that while awareness of disaster preparedness is present, a gap exists between the levels of understanding among barangay residents and DRRMC members.

DRRMC members demonstrate a higher level of awareness, with a mean score of 3.64 ("Strongly Agree"), compared to barangay residents, who recorded a lower mean score of 2.77 ("Agree"). This indicates that those directly involved in disaster response efforts are significantly more knowledgeable about preparedness measures, whereas barangay residents may require further education and engagement in emergency response training.

The highest-ranked item, "A Public Storm Signal warning tells the general public what to expect and provides an advisory of necessary precautions during typhoons" (mean = 3.265, Rank 1), suggests that respondents are well aware of storm warning systems and their role in disaster preparedness. Similarly, the second highest-ranked item, "Rescue, Alert, Contain, Extinguish (R.A.C.E) is a simulated-based response to a fire hazard drill (mean = 3.22, Rank 2), highlighting strong awareness of fire response procedures, which is crucial for mitigating fire-related disasters.

Other key indicators such as "Specialized training and simulation exercises are only given to specific groups (e.g., decision-makers, responders, public/private sector employees, etc.) to help them prepare for disasters" (mean = 3.21, Rank 3) and "When utilizing a fire extinguisher, the acronym P.A.S.S stands for Pull, Aim, Sweep, and Squeeze" (mean = 3.21, Rank 3) reflect a moderate awareness of targeted disaster training and fire safety measures. However, these findings also suggest that emergency training programs are not widely accessible to the general public, which may limit community-wide preparedness.

The lowest-ranked item, "Drop, Cover, and Hold On is a simulated-based response to an earthquake drill" (mean = 3.165, Rank 10), suggests that while respondents are aware of earthquake safety protocols, this aspect of preparedness may require further reinforcement through regular drills and training programs. Similarly, "Disaster Risk Reduction and Management information, education, communication (IEC), and advocacy enhance the community's awareness and capacity for dealing with the threats and impacts of all hazards" (mean = 3.18, Rank 8) indicates that while communication strategies exist, their effectiveness in reaching and educating the broader community may need improvement.

Overall, the study highlights a higher level of awareness among DRRMC members compared to barangay residents, emphasizing the need for more inclusive disaster preparedness programs at the community level. Efforts should be directed toward increasing public participation in scenario-based drills, improving access to specialized training, and strengthening information dissemination strategies to ensure that all residents, regardless of their level of involvement in disaster management, are adequately prepared for emergencies.

Table 2.3 indicates that both barangay residents and DRRMC members generally agree on the importance of disaster response strategies in the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) initiatives. The overall mean score of 3.19 ("Agree") suggests that while respondents recognize the significance of response efforts, there are varying levels of awareness, particularly between barangay residents and DRRMC members.

DRRMC members demonstrate a higher level of awareness, with a mean score of 3.64 ("Strongly Agree"), compared to barangay residents, who recorded a lower mean score of 2.75 ("Agree"). This suggests that those directly involved in disaster response operations have a deeper understanding of emergency protocols, whereas barangay residents may require additional education and training in disaster response strategies.

The highest-ranked item, "Food, shelter, water, and sanitation, and health preservation are the basic requirements addressed when an emergency disaster strikes" (mean = 3.235, Rank 1), suggests that respondents are aware of the fundamental necessities during disaster response. Additionally, "Traumatic and/or psychological stress debriefing is provided to address the physiological needs of the affected population, especially the elderly, persons with disabilities, women, and children" (mean = 3.215, Rank 2) highlights the recognition of mental health support as a crucial component of disaster response.

Other key indicators, such as "Basic social services such as medical consultation and nutritional assessment are provided to the affected population to maintain the health status of affected communities" (mean = 3.2, Rank 3) and "The success of a functional, integrated, and coordinated system to assist victims throughout their early recovery is dependent on the political commitment of both the local and national governments" (mean = 3.195, Rank 4), emphasize the need for continued government commitment and support in disaster recovery efforts.

The lowest-ranked item, "The DRRM team sorts sick and injured people based on their frequency and type of condition, a process called 'Triage'" (mean = 3.165, Rank 10), suggests that while respondents are aware of the triage system, additional education may be required to improve public understanding of medical response prioritization during disasters. Similarly, "Disaster victims categorized in 'black code' are considered the first, immediate, and high priority under Triage" (mean = 3.175, Rank 9) suggests that while triage systems are recognized, there may be misconceptions about prioritization protocols.

Overall, the study reveals a higher level of awareness among DRRMC members compared to barangay residents, underscoring the need for enhanced community-based education on disaster response and preparedness. Efforts should be directed toward strengthening public knowledge of medical response procedures, evacuation protocols, and government coordination to ensure a well-prepared and resilient community during a disaster.

Table 2.4 indicates that barangay residents and DRRMC members generally agree on the importance of rehabilitation and recovery in Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) efforts in the City Government of Muntinlupa. The overall mean score of 3.23 ("Agree") indicates a moderate level of awareness regarding post-disaster recovery strategies, with DRRMC members exhibiting significantly higher awareness, at 3.68 ("Strongly Agree"), compared to barangay residents, who scored 2.79 ("Agree"). This discrepancy highlights the need for greater community engagement in post-disaster recovery initiatives.

The highest-ranked item, "Managing recovery requires building local capacities, restoring coping mechanisms, empowering communities, and determining the root causes and vulnerabilities that make the communities disaster-free" (mean = 3.27, Rank 1), indicates that respondents acknowledge the importance of strengthening local resilience as a foundation for sustainable recovery. Similarly, "People's ability to recover quickly from disasters depends heavily on restoring their sources of income and livelihood opportunities" (mean = 3.26, Rank 2) emphasizes that economic recovery plays a crucial role in rehabilitation efforts.

Other key indicators, such as "DRRM is mainstreamed in human settlement and safety for people displaced by natural and human-induced disasters and those living in disaster-free areas" (mean = 3.255, Rank 3) and "A psychologically sound, safe, and secure citizenry protected from the effects of disasters can restore subnormal functioning after each disaster" (mean = 3.25, Rank 4), suggest that respondents recognize the importance of both physical safety and mental well-being in disaster recovery.

Meanwhile, the lowest-ranked items, "DRRM authorities coordinate formulating the Strategic Action Plan for disaster-affected areas locally and nationally" and "LGUs, NGOs, concerned agencies, and other private sector organizations fund disaster victims' recovery" (mean = 3.2, Rank 9), suggest that while respondents acknowledge the role of coordination and funding in rehabilitation efforts, these aspects may require further emphasis and transparency to ensure more inclusive recovery programs.

Overall, the study reveals a higher level of awareness among DRRMC members compared to barangay residents, underscoring the need for more comprehensive public education campaigns and participatory initiatives to engage the broader community in rehabilitation and recovery efforts. Enhancing livelihood restoration programs, integrating mental health support into recovery plans, and improving public knowledge of strategic post-disaster planning could further strengthen the resilience of Muntinlupa's disaster-affected communities.

Table 3.1 indicates that both barangay residents and DRRMC members generally agree on the effectiveness of the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) practices in terms of mitigation and prevention. The overall mean score of 2.68 ("Agree") suggests that while disaster mitigation efforts are recognized, there is still room for improvement in strengthening community preventive measures.

Both barangay residents, 2.66 ("Agree"), and DRRMC members, 2.70 ("Agree"), share similar perceptions, with the latter having a slightly higher evaluation. This indicates that those directly involved in disaster management have a marginally more favorable view of the city's mitigation initiatives than the general community.

The highest-ranked item, "Utilization of the local DRRM funds for barangays and communities" (mean = 2.755, Rank 1), suggests respondents acknowledge the financial support allocated for disaster prevention and mitigation efforts. However, despite this recognition, the relatively moderate rating indicates that further improvements in fund allocation, transparency, and efficiency may still be necessary.

Other well-rated aspects include "Mainstreaming and integrating Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) into local development policies, plans, programs, and budgets" (mean = 2.695, Rank 2) and "Developing community-based and local early warning systems for various hazards in barangays and communities" (mean = 2.695, Rank 2). These results highlight that respondents recognize the importance of proactive planning and early warning systems in disaster mitigation, although further enhancements in implementation may be beneficial.

Meanwhile, areas such as "Developing advocacy and risk communication plans for barangays and communities" (mean = 2.595, Rank 10) and "Conducting inventory, vulnerability, and risk assessments of critical facilities in the barangays and communities" (mean = 2.665, Rank 9) ranked the lowest. This suggests that communication strategies and risk assessment efforts may not be as effective or widely implemented as other DRRM measures.

Overall, the findings emphasize that while Muntinlupa's DRRM mitigation and prevention strategies are generally acknowledged as present and functional, there is a need to enhance communication, improve risk assessment strategies, and maximize the use of local DRRM funds to ensure a more resilient and disaster-prepared community. Strengthening awareness campaigns, upgrading infrastructure safety standards, and ensuring that all barangays have robust early warning systems can further improve disaster risk reduction in the city.

Table 3.2 indicates that both barangay residents and DRRMC members generally agree on the effectiveness of the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) preparedness efforts. The overall mean score of 2.70 ("Agree") suggests that while preparedness initiatives are recognized as present and functional, there is room for improvement in further strengthening disaster readiness at the barangay level.

A comparison of responses shows that DRRMC members rated preparedness efforts 2.74 ("Agree"), slightly higher than barangay residents, who rated them 2.66 ("Agree"), respectively. This suggests that those directly involved in disaster response perceive the city's preparedness strategies as more effective than the general community.

This discrepancy highlights the need for better public engagement and communication regarding DRRM programs.

The highest-ranked item, "Develop and/or enhance ICS coordination and communication systems for barangays and communities" (mean = 2.735, Rank 1), suggests that respondents recognize the importance of an effective Incident Command System (ICS) and communication infrastructure in ensuring coordinated disaster response. Likewise, "Develop and/or enhance a manual of operations for Disaster Operations Centers for barangays and communities" (mean = 2.72, Rank 2) emphasizes the need for well-documented response protocols to streamline disaster operations.

Other highly rated aspects include "Managing resources of the Local DRRM Councils and Offices for barangays and communities" (mean = 2.715, Rank 3) and "Develop and/or enhance protocols for information gathering and reporting" (mean = 2.71, Rank 4). These findings highlight that respondents see resource management and adequate information flow as essential components of disaster preparedness.

Meanwhile, the lowest-ranked items, "Development of the local DRRM and contingency plan for barangays and communities" (mean = 2.68, Rank 10) and "Conduct training and simulation exercises in barangays and communities" (mean = 2.685, Rank 8), suggest that while these preparedness strategies are acknowledged, they may not be as actively implemented or widely participated in as other DRRM activities. This could indicate a need for more frequent and community-inclusive training programs to ensure that residents are adequately prepared for disasters.

Overall, the findings suggest that while Muntinlupa's DRRM preparedness initiatives are generally effective, enhancing public participation, conducting more simulation exercises, and strengthening contingency planning at the barangay level could further improve the city's disaster readiness. Efforts should also focus on improving coordination, communication, and resource allocation to ensure a well-prepared and resilient community.

Table 3.3 indicates that both barangay residents and DRRMC members generally agree on the effectiveness of the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) response efforts. The overall mean score of 2.58 ("Agree") suggests that while response measures are present, there is room for further improvement, particularly in key areas such as post-disaster assessment and medical support services.

A comparison of responses shows that DRRMC members rated response efforts 2.62 ("Agree") slightly higher than barangay residents, who rated them 2.55 ("Agree"), suggesting that those directly involved in disaster response perceive these measures as more effective. However, both groups rated some areas lower, indicating gaps that need to be addressed in emergency response operations.

The highest-ranked item, "Develop and implement systems for search, rescue, and retrieval (SRR)" (mean = 2.73, Rank 1), indicates that respondents recognize the importance of well-structured search, rescue, and retrieval efforts in disaster response. Likewise, "Identify standard-based relief shelters and sites in the barangays and communities" (mean = 2.725, Rank 2) emphasizes the importance of establishing proper evacuation and relief centers for disaster victims.

Other highly rated aspects include "Establishment of coordination systems for effective and efficient relief and response operations" (mean = 2.72, Rank 3) and "Design and implement temporary livelihood and/or income-generating activities (i.e., cash/food for work; micro and small enterprise recovery) for barangays and communities" (mean = 2.715, Rank 4). These findings suggest that respondents see coordination, relief operations, and economic recovery as essential elements of an effective disaster response.

Meanwhile, the lowest-ranked items, "Conduct an assessment using the latest damage assessment and needs analysis (DANA) tool with the barangay and community, using the information to inform the appropriate response of the DRRM council" (mean = 2.265, Rank 10) and "Conduct post-DANA for the affected barangays and communities" (mean = 2.27, Rank 9), suggest that damage assessment and needs analysis procedures are either not well understood, not fully implemented, or not effectively communicated to barangay residents.

Similarly, "Conduct medical consultations, nutritional assessments, and traumatic and/or psychological stress debriefings in the barangays and communities" (mean = 2.32, Rank 8) received a relatively low rating, particularly from barangay residents (2.26, "Disagree"), indicating that post-disaster healthcare services, including psychosocial support and trauma debriefing, may be insufficient or not widely accessible in affected communities.

Overall, the findings suggest that while Muntinlupa's DRRM response strategies are functional, improvements are needed in damage assessment procedures, post-disaster healthcare services, and emergency response coordination at the barangay level. Strengthening public awareness, enhancing assessment protocols, and ensuring that medical and psychological support reaches all affected individuals can improve the city's disaster response and recovery efforts.

Table 3.4 indicates that both barangay residents and DRRMC members generally agree on the effectiveness of the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) rehabilitation and recovery efforts. The overall mean score of 2.61 ("Agree") suggests that, although rehabilitation and recovery measures are in place, there is still room for improvement. Specifically, in key areas such as conducting a Post-Disaster Needs Assessment (PDNA), conducting post-disaster and conflict needs analyses, and building the capacities of psychosocial care providers, there is a need for enhancement.

A comparison of responses shows that DRRMC members rated rehabilitation and recovery efforts 2.67 ("Agree") slightly higher than barangay residents, who rated them 2.55 ("Agree"), suggesting that those directly involved in disaster response perceive these measures as more effective. However, both groups rated some areas lower, indicating gaps that need to be addressed in rehabilitation and recovery programs.

The two highest-ranked items, "Identify and mobilize funding sources for barangays and communities, and Identify and provide suitable relocation sites for the affected barangays and communities" (mean = 2.735, Rank 1), underscore the importance of these actions in the eyes of the respondents. This observation of available funds and relocation sites for the affected barangays and communities provides reassurance about the future of disaster victims. Similarly, "Coordinate formulating the Strategic Action Plan for disaster-affected barangays and communities" (mean = 2.73, Rank 3) emphasizes the importance of coordination and planning for disaster victims, further reinforcing this sense of reassurance.

Other highly rated aspects include "Develop systems of support and communication among key stakeholders" (mean = 2.71, Rank 4) and "Undertake the necessary rehabilitation or repair of damaged infrastructure in the barangays and communities" (mean = 2.7, Rank 5). These findings are significant as they suggest that respondents observe systematic communication and support as well as an immediate rehabilitation program. Their active participation and feedback are crucial for the success of the DRRM rehabilitation and recovery efforts.

Meanwhile, the lowest-ranked items, "Build capacities of psychosocial care providers for affected barangays and communities" (mean = 2.335, Rank 10), and "Conduct post-disaster/conflict needs analyses with affected barangays and communities" (mean = 2.365, Rank 9), highlight the urgent need to provide psychosocial care providers and conduct post-disaster/conflict needs analyses for disaster victims. These findings underscore the urgency of the situation and the need for immediate action.

Similarly, "Conduct a Post-Disaster Needs Assessment (PDNA) one month after a disaster occurs with the affected barangays and communities. The OCD will take the lead and use preliminary data gathered from the field by OCD regional offices" (mean = 2.37, Rank 8) received a relatively low rating, particularly from barangay residents, indicating that the Post-Disaster Needs Assessment (PDNA) for a holistic rehabilitation and recovery program for disaster victims.

Overall, the findings of this study underscore the need for improvement in Muntinlupa's DRRM rehabilitation and recovery strategies. Particularly, in providing psychosocial care, conducting Post-Disaster Analyses and Needs Assessments. These findings are crucial for the future effectiveness of disaster response and recovery efforts.

Table 4 reveals a significant relationship between the respondents' level of awareness and their assessment of the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) practices. The mean score of 3.19 for awareness,

with a standard deviation of 0.434, indicates that respondents generally have a moderate to high understanding of DRRM initiatives. Meanwhile, the mean score of 2.64 for the assessment, with a standard deviation of 0.148, suggests that while respondents acknowledge the presence of DRRM efforts, they perceive a need for improvement in implementation and effectiveness.

The Pearson r value of 0.247 demonstrates a low but positive correlation between awareness and assessment. As awareness of DRRM practices increases, so does the respondents' evaluation of these initiatives. The critical value of ± 1.96 leads to rejecting the null hypothesis, confirming a statistically significant relationship between the two variables.

This finding implies that higher awareness levels contribute to a more favorable assessment of DRRM efforts, reinforcing the importance of continuous information dissemination, training, and community engagement in disaster preparedness and response. The relatively low correlation suggests that other factors—such as direct experience with disaster response, resource availability, or policy enforcement—may also influence how DRRM practices are perceived.

To further strengthen DRRM initiatives in Muntinlupa, the local government may need to enhance public awareness campaigns, conduct more community-based drills, and improve transparency in disaster management policies. The city can build a more resilient and well-informed community by bridging the gap between awareness and the actual implementation of DRRM strategies.

Table 5 indicates no significant difference between barangay residents and DRRMC members' assessment of the City Government of Muntinlupa's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) capability. The mean score for residents is 2.68, with a standard deviation (SD) of 0.134, while DRRMC members have a higher mean score of 3.15, with a standard deviation of 0.483. This suggests that DRRMC officials perceive the city's DRRM capability more favorably than community residents.

However, the computed t -test value of 0.0003 is within the critical value range of ± 1.04 , leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This means that the difference in perception between the two groups is not statistically significant. Despite the numerical gap in their mean assessments, the statistical analysis suggests that both groups generally share a similar perspective on the city's DRRM efforts.

The slightly lower assessment from residents may indicate a gap in public perception and engagement, where community members may not fully experience or be aware of the DRRM measures implemented by the local government. On the other hand, DRRMC members directly involved in disaster management may have a more comprehensive understanding of the city's capabilities and initiatives.

This finding underscores the need for more robust community participation, enhanced public communication, and increased transparency in DRRM programs to

bridge the gap between government-led initiatives and residents' awareness and perception of these efforts. Strengthening disaster education, increasing community involvement in planning and drills, and enhancing accessibility to DRRM services may help align the perspectives of both groups, fostering a more resilient and prepared community.

Conclusions

The study highlights that disaster risk reduction and management efforts in Muntinlupa are predominantly led by individuals aged 25-44, reflecting an active workforce engaged in disaster preparedness and response. However, participation significantly declines among older age groups, indicating a potential for more inclusive disaster management initiatives that encourage broader community involvement across different age groups. Both men and women actively engage in disaster-related matters at the community level. Still, the gender imbalance in DRRM leadership highlights the need for policies that promote greater inclusivity and gender equality in disaster risk reduction and management efforts in Muntinlupa. Encouraging more female participation in DRRM roles could help diversify perspectives and enhance disaster preparedness strategies. The study shows that disaster management in Muntinlupa is primarily driven by married individuals, highlighting the importance of family-oriented disaster preparedness strategies. The relatively low participation of single and widowed individuals in DRRMC roles may indicate a need to encourage broader community engagement across different marital statuses to enhance disaster resilience. The study highlights that disaster risk reduction and management in Muntinlupa are primarily handled by individuals with a college-level education, particularly those with a Bachelor's Degree. However, the presence of barangay residents with lower educational attainment suggests that efforts should be made to enhance disaster education and awareness programs at the grassroots level. Additionally, integrating more professionals with advanced degrees into DRRMC roles may further strengthen the city's disaster preparedness and strategic planning efforts. The data suggest that all barangays in Muntinlupa have some level of disaster management participation, with Brgy. Tunasan and Brgy. Poblacion leading in engagement. However, efforts may be needed to strengthen DRRM initiatives in barangays with lower representation, such as Brgy. Sucat, to ensure equitable disaster preparedness and response across the entire city. Long-term residents dominate barangay and DRRMC groups; efforts could be made to involve newer residents in disaster preparedness programs. Doing so may encourage fresh perspectives, knowledge transfer, and continuity in disaster risk reduction strategies for future generations.

The study highlights a higher level of awareness among DRRMC members compared to barangay residents, underscoring the need for more comprehensive public education campaigns and participatory initiatives to engage the broader community in rehabilitation and recovery efforts. Efforts should be directed toward increasing public participation in scenario-based drills, improving access to specialized training, and strengthening information dissemination strategies to ensure that all residents, regardless of their level of involvement in disaster management, are adequately prepared for

emergencies. The study also reveals a higher level of awareness among DRRMC members compared to barangay residents, emphasizing the need for more inclusive disaster preparedness programs at the community level. Efforts should be directed toward increasing public participation in scenario-based drills, improving access to specialized training, and strengthening information dissemination strategies to ensure that all residents, regardless of their level of involvement in disaster management, are adequately prepared for emergencies. The study reveals a higher level of awareness among DRRMC members compared to barangay residents, underscoring the need for enhanced community-based education on disaster response and preparedness. Efforts should be directed toward strengthening public knowledge of medical response procedures, evacuation protocols, and government coordination to ensure a well-prepared and resilient community during a disaster. Further, the study reveals a higher level of awareness among DRRMC members compared to barangay residents, underscoring the need for more comprehensive public education campaigns and participatory initiatives to engage the broader community in rehabilitation and recovery efforts. Enhancing livelihood restoration programs, integrating mental health support into recovery plans, and improving public knowledge of strategic post-disaster planning could further strengthen the resilience of Muntinlupa's disaster-affected communities.

The study emphasizes that while Muntinlupa's DRRM mitigation and prevention strategies are generally acknowledged as present and functional, there is a need to enhance communication, improve risk assessment strategies, and maximize the use of local DRRM funds to ensure a more resilient and disaster-prepared community. Strengthening awareness campaigns, upgrading infrastructure safety standards, and ensuring that all barangays have robust early warning systems can further improve disaster risk reduction in the city. The study also suggests that while Muntinlupa's DRRM preparedness initiatives are generally effective, enhancing public participation, conducting more simulation exercises, and strengthening contingency planning at the barangay level could further improve the city's disaster readiness. Efforts should also focus on improving coordination, communication, and resource allocation to ensure a well-prepared and resilient community. The study suggests that while Muntinlupa's DRRM response strategies are functional, improvements are needed in damage assessment procedures, post-disaster healthcare services, and emergency response coordination at the barangay level. These improvements are urgent and crucial for the city's disaster response and recovery efforts. Lastly, the study underscores the need for improvement in Muntinlupa's DRRM rehabilitation and recovery strategies. Particularly, in providing psychosocial care, conducting Post-Disaster Analyses and Needs Assessments. These findings are crucial for the future effectiveness of disaster response and recovery efforts.

The data imply that higher awareness levels contribute to a more favorable assessment of DRRM efforts. However, the relatively low correlation suggests that the influence of other factors—such as direct experience with disaster response, resource availability, or policy enforcement—should not be underestimated in shaping perceptions of DRRM practices.

The study underscores the need for more robust community participation, enhanced public communication, and increased transparency in DRRM programs to bridge the gap between government-led initiatives and residents' awareness and perception of these efforts. Strengthening disaster education, increasing community involvement in planning and drills, and enhancing accessibility to DRRM services may help align the perspectives of both groups, fostering a more resilient and prepared community. The data imply that higher awareness levels contribute to a more favorable assessment of DRRM efforts, reinforcing the importance of continuous information dissemination, training, and community engagement in disaster preparedness and response. The relatively low correlation suggests that other factors, such as direct experience with disaster response, resource availability, or policy enforcement, may also influence how DRRM practices are perceived.

Recommendations

It is strongly recommended that the Post-Disaster Needs Assessment (PDNA) be integrated into the City's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) processes. PDNA compiles data on the physical effects of a disaster, the economic value of the damages and losses, the human repercussions felt by the impacted population, and the associated short- and long-term recovery needs and priorities. This comprehensive approach enables the development of recovery plans tailored to current socioeconomic needs, ensuring that all relevant factors are considered when creating comprehensive programs. These programs are designed to benefit the most impacted barangays or communities, thereby maximizing the effectiveness of the recovery process (Jeggle & Boggero, 2021).

Key benefits of conducting a post-disaster/conflict needs analysis:

a. **Prioritizing Recovery Efforts**

PDNA is crucial in identifying the most pressing needs across various sectors, including health, infrastructure, housing, and livelihoods. This identification enables the efficient allocation of resources and interventions, thereby maximizing their impact.

b. **Evidence-Based Decision Making**

The comprehensive data gathered through a PDNA provides a robust foundation for making informed decisions regarding recovery planning, resource mobilization, and project design. This ensures that interventions are aligned with the actual needs of the affected population.

c. **Stakeholder Engagement**

PDNA, as an approach, often involves active engagement from local communities, government agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and international organizations. This engagement fosters collaboration and ownership of the recovery strategy, ensuring that it truly reflects the needs and priorities of the affected population.

d. Improved Coordination

A PDNA improves coordination among the various actors involved in the recovery process by providing a consistent image of the post-disaster condition. This minimizes duplication of efforts and gaps in aid, ensuring a more organized recovery process.

e. Monitoring and Evaluation

A PDNA serves as a baseline for monitoring progress and assessing the efficacy of recovery programs over time.

f. Building Resilience

A PDNA can help improve community resilience and readiness for future crises by identifying the vulnerabilities that a disaster exposes.

g. Advocacy and Resource Mobilization

The complete data from a PDNA can be utilized to appeal for funding and support from donors and international organizations (McFarlane & Williams, 2012).

Essential components of a post-disaster/conflict needs analysis:

a. Multisectoral Approach

Assessing requirements in various sectors, including health, education, shelter, infrastructure, livelihoods, and psychosocial well-being.

b. Community Engagement

Conducting participatory evaluations to obtain firsthand descriptions of needs and priorities from affected communities.

c. Rapid Assessment

Conducting a quick initial evaluation to identify immediate needs in the aftermath of a disaster.

d. Gender-sensitivity Analysis

Consider the needs and vulnerabilities of the impacted population, including both men and women (McFarlane & Williams, 2012).

It is highly recommended that psychological care providers be implemented and used in affected barangays and communities. These providers play a pivotal role during and after disasters by offering emotional support, assisting individuals in processing trauma, building resilience, and connecting them with necessary resources. Their role is not just about addressing physical needs but also about understanding and addressing the psychological impact of the disaster. This can include providing immediate crisis intervention, facilitating community connections, and identifying individuals who require additional mental health support. Providing information, practical assistance, and emotional and compassionate support is critical. It is also vital to prioritize assistance for those who require the most psychosocial support. Screening for high-risk responses is needed. Debriefing crisis team members was also necessary (Capala, 2024).

Key benefits of providing psychosocial care in crises:

a. Immediate Support

They can offer "Psychological First Aid" (PFA), which helps people calm their emotions, feel comfortable, and access basic coping skills in the immediate aftermath of a crisis.

b. Trauma Processing

Trained specialists can assist individuals in understanding and processing their traumatic events, minimizing the risk of long-term psychological consequences such as PTSD.

c. Resilience Building

Psychosocial therapies can educate people on coping mechanisms and resilience methods to help them manage stress and recover from adversity.

d. Community Engagement

They can lead group sessions to encourage social connection, shared coping, and community support among affected people.

e. Identification of Needs

Psychosocial providers can detect people who are experiencing significant psychological distress and refer them to the necessary mental health care.

f. Supporting First Responders

They can provide mental health support to emergency personnel who are typically subjected to substantial trauma during disaster response.

g. Advocacy and Awareness

They can advocate for the inclusion of mental health services in disaster recovery plans and raise awareness about the importance of psychosocial support (Zahos et al., 2022).

Specific interventions offered by psychosocial care providers:

a. Active Listening and Empathy

Providing a secure environment where people can communicate their emotions and experiences without fear of judgment.

b. Stress Management Techniques

Teach relaxation techniques, breathing exercises, and other coping strategies.

c. Grief Counseling

Assisting people who have suffered losses as a result of the disaster.

d. Community Outreach

Engaging with affected communities to determine their needs and provide accessible assistance (Zahos et al., 2022).

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Informed consent, obtained through a comprehensive and transparent process, was secured from all individual participants included in the study. This research strictly adheres to the principles of the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest. All authors have thoroughly reviewed and unanimously agree with the contents of the manuscript, further ensuring the ethical conduct of this research.

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